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SECU-ME: A SELF-DESTRUCTION APPLICATION BASED ON TIME

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Abstract:

Objective- Cloud computing means storing and accessing data and programs over the Internet instead of your computer's hard drive. The cloud is just a metaphor for the Internet. Cloud computing is a type of computing that relies on sharing computing resources rather than having local servers or personal devices to handle applications. Cloud computing is often touted as the future of business and enterprise technology where people are subjected to post their personal information like passwords, account number and different confidential data. It is possible to access data stored in the cloud by intruders or a third person. So the main concern is to provide security of the stored data in the cloud. For ensuring such security self destruction scheme is proposed.

Design / Methodology/ Approach- A Client-Server approach is used in this system. A cloud server is the main server used, and the user application part is the client part. There is a database for storing the client details. The multicloud feature enables the user to retain the shared data.

Findings- Self destruction of data from the cloud storage is the key feature if this system. All the data get self destructed after a user specified duration. AES algorithm is used for the encryption and decryption. After user specified time period message sent by the sender should be destructed. Any legitimate user can download file till the timeout if and only if the sender is granted permission for that. The file should be encrypted before sending and the decryption of the message is happened to the device after receiving it. By using AES algorithm the users can encrypt their files using and thus making more complexity to the hijackers or he/she cannot decrypt the files more easily. So it reduces major security and privacy issues in the cloud server and can overcome the manual deletion of confidential data's from cloud server.

Limitations- Storing of data's to personal devices are restricted for ensuring security but it has to be taken into consideration.

Practical implications- This paper is very helpful for those who require sharing their confidential data and to kept more securely using multicloud methodology.

Originality/Value- The value of this paper is expanding the privacy of shared data in cloud and automatic implicit deletion of data from cloud .It increases the processing speed by self destruction of data on time basis since dumping of data's in cloud can be avoided.

Keywords- Cloud server, AES algorithm Cipher text, Encryption, Decryption, iCloud

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 OVERVIEW

Cloud computing is a term used to describe a new class of network based computing that takes place over the internet. Cloud group consists of large number of files; manual removal is not practical in real world. So, automatic removal of shared files is needed. A self destruction can be used to solve this problem which automatically removes unwanted files. A self destruction can be used to solve this problem which automatically removes unwanted files. But, still it experience problem in removing files. Because, some files may need for a long time sharing whereas few may not. Therefore automatic removal of files is not applicable here, as it can't differentiate which file is needed and which is not.

So we are proposing “SECU-ME” an iOS mobile application which works on self destruction scheme. In this application is based on Client – Server model. The client side done in iOS platform and the server side is in the cloud server storage.

SECU-ME self-destruction system is based on time. A new user to this application should do the registration process for accessing the entry. User registers with the system by providing the necessary details like First name, Last name, Email ID and Password. After successful registration user can login to the system by providing user name and password. Then the user becomes the authorized user for accessing the application. For each registered user can gain access to our SECU-ME application by identifying and authenticating themselves.

After successful registration and login to SECU-ME user enters to the next interface for sending message. Messages can be sent to an existing user or to a new user by creating a new contact. Message can be text or an attachment. For providing security there is an option for setting time slot for each message sending by the user. By setting such a timeslot, sender is

fixing the time after which the message will be self destructed from the server. The sender can also decide whether the receiver can save the received message to their personal cloud (iCloud).The sender send the message after the encryption process. For ensuring more security, AES algorithm is using. The users can encrypt their files using AES technique thus making the task of a hacker more complicated or he/she cannot decrypt the files more easily. Messages reached to the cloud server, there by the receiver receives the message and decrypt it. Every messages received should have a time slot assigned by the sender in which if the time to live field is not expired then user can receive the data. User won't be able to access the data after the time to live value expires. After the time out if user is trying to access the data then it gives message-“sorry the message seems to be expired.. If the receiver wants to save or download the received message contents, it is only possible when the sender has granted with permission for that. If the sender allows the permission to save the message to receiver, can save it to the storage personal cloud/icloud otherwise can see or read the message until it gets expired.

1.1.1 ENHANCING SECURITY IN CLOUD BY SELF-DESTRUCTION MECHANISM

Cloud computing, a recent computing technology is preferred by most of the users to store their data. Large amount of data can be stored in cloud. Due to easy access and availability cloud services are becoming very important in people's life. People are desired to post personal private information to the cloud by the internet. People hope that service provider will provide security to their data stored in cloud. Security and privacy are the main concern for the data stored in cloud. Data stored in cloud is replicated in many nodes and authorized user does not have information about the storage of these copies. Unauthorized users can access these data and can store it for their future use. Cloud Service Providers negligence, hacker's intrusion or legal action is also responsible for imparting the privacy.

Vanish supplies a new idea for sharing and protecting privacy of data. In Vanish secret key is divided and stored in a P2P system with distributed hash tables (DHTs).Length range of key shares was increased in Safe Vanish. This increased the attack cost but was unable to control the attack to large extent. This paper presents a solution to implement self-destructing data system. Self-destruct method defines two new modules, self-destruct method that is associated with each secret key part and survival time parameter for each secret key part. Shamir secret sharing algorithm is used to generate key shares.

Proposed FADE which is built upon standard cryptographic techniques. FADE is readily deployable cloud technique used to protect deleted data with policy based file based assured deletion. FADE is built upon standard cryptographic techniques. Vanish is a system that automatically self-destruct data after a period of time. It integrates cryptographic techniques with global-scale, P2P, distributed hash tables (DHTs). DHT have a property of discarding data older than certain age. Key with which data is encrypted is permanently lost hence encrypted data becomes permanently unreadable.

Self-destructive system describes two new modules, a self-destruct method that is linked with each secret key part and each secret key part is associated with survival time parameter. Self destructive architecture consists of mainly 4 blocks-Metadata server, User layer, Security layer, Storage node. Different modules used in the proposed system are Development of Login System, Secret Key Part, File uploading, Self-Destruction Method, Downloading File.

1.1.2 A SURVEY ON SECURE DATA SELF-DESTRUCTING SCHEME IN CLOUD COMPUTING

With the rapid development of versatile cloud services, it becomes increasingly susceptible to use cloud services to share data in a friend circle in the cloud computing environment. Since it is not feasible to implement full lifecycle privacy security, access control becomes a challenging task, especially when it shares sensitive data on cloud servers. In order to tackle this problem, So a key-policy attribute-based encryption with time -specified attributes (KPTSABE), a novel secure data self-destructing scheme in cloud computing. The KP-TSABE is able to solve some important security problems by supporting user defined authorization period and by providing fine-grained access control during the period. The sensitive data will be securely self-destructed after a user-specified expiration time. The KP-TSABE scheme is proved to be secure under the decision 1-bilinear Diffie-Hellman inversion (1-Expanded BDHI) assumption.

Data owner can provide data or files that contain some sensitive information, which are used for sharing with his/her friends (data users). All these shared data are outsourced to the

cloud servers to store. Authority is an indispensable entity which is responsible for generating, distributing and managing all the private keys, and is trusted by all the other entities involved in the system. Time Server is a time reference server without any interaction with other entities involved in the system. It is responsible for a precise release time specification.

Data users are some peoples who passed the identity authentication and access to the data outsourced by the data owner. Notice that, the shared data can only be accessed by the authorized users during its authorization period. Cloud Servers contains almost unlimited storage space which is able to store and manage all the data or files in the system. Other entities with limited storage space can store their data to the cloud servers. Potential Adversary is a polynomial time adversary and described in the security model of the KP-TSABE scheme.

Data privacy is essential in the Cloud environment. A new approach is introduced for protecting the data privacy from attackers which may obtain, from legal or other means, a user's stored data and private decryption keys. A novel aspect is the leveraging of the essential properties of active storage framework based on T10OSD standard. Personal data stored in the cloud may contain account numbers, secret codes and other necessary details that could be used and misused. SeDas uses the self-destruct operation without any action on the user's part. Measurement and experimental security analysis sheds insight into the practicability of this approach.

1.1.3 A SECURE DATA SELF-DESTRUCTING SCHEME IN CLOUD COMPUTING

When a data owner wants to share someone his/her information, the owner must know exactly the one he/she wants to share with. In many applications, the data owner wants to share information with several users according to the security policy based on the users' credentials. Attribute based encryption (ABE) has significant advantages based on the tradition public key encryption instead of one-to-one encryption because it achieves flexible one-to-many encryption. In the key-policy ABE (KP-ABE) scheme to be elaborated in this paper, the cipher text is labelled with set of descriptive attributes.

With the rapid development of versatile cloud services, a lot of new challenges have emerged. One of the most important problems is how to securely delete the outsourced data stored in the cloud servers. In this paper, they proposed a novel KP-TSABE scheme which is able

to achieve the time-specified ciphertext in order to solve these problems by implementing flexible fine-grained access control during the authorization period and time-controllable self-destruction after expiration to the shared and outsourced data in cloud computing. They also gave a system model and a security model for the KPTSABE scheme. Furthermore, they proved that KPTSABE is secure under the standard model with the decision 1-Expanded BDHI assumption. The comprehensive analysis indicates that the proposed KP-TSABE scheme is superior to other existing schemes.

In this paper, they propose a KP-TSABE scheme, which is a novel secure self-destructing scheme for data sharing in cloud computing. First introduce the notion of KP-TSABE, formalize the model of KP-TSABE and give the security model of it. Then, we give a specific construction method about the scheme. Finally, we prove that the KP-TSABE scheme is secure.

1.1.4 TIME BASED SELF-DESTRUCTION SYSTEM FOR SECURE DATA SHARING IN CLOUD

This paper proposed a self-destruction system based on time. In this, each data owner has to specify a time limit up to which the files are available for sharing in the cloud while uploading the files to the cloud. When the time expires, the files will be automatically self destructed from the cloud. If the user wants to retain the deleted files, we have also proposed a multi-cloud feature in which the files will be deleted only from the shared cloud while it is kept as such in the data cloud .So the user can again upload the file if needed. Security and privacy issues still remain as challenges. For ensuring more security, multiple encryption techniques (AES-256 and 3DES) are used. The users can encrypt their files using any of these techniques thus making the task of a hacker more complicated or he/she cannot decrypt the files more easily.

This paper describes about the Existing system i.e. the Vanish and Fade concepts. Vanish is a system for creating messages that automatically self-destruct after a period of time. In vanish system a secret key is divided and stored in a point to point system with distributed hash tables (DHTs). With the joining and exiting of point to point method, the system can maintain secure

keys. According to characteristics of point to point, after eight hours the DHT will refresh every node. Vanish uses Shamir secret key algorithm. DHTs discard data older than a certain age. The key is permanently lost, and encrypted data is permanently unreadable after data expiration. Another system called FADE, provide contribution for the self destructing data by integrating cryptographic techniques. The data will be encrypted before sending it. The system will delete the files and makes them unrecoverable by revoking the file access permission. FADE which is built upon standard cryptographic techniques and assuredly deletes files to make them unrecoverable to anyone upon revocations of file access policies.

This paper proposed a secure self destruction system in cloud computing. For ensuring more security multiple encryption techniques were used. We also included a multi cloud feature for the recovery of the destructed file if it is further needed. Hence in this self destruction system all the files are removed automatically as the time expires. This system will reduce complexity in managing old data files and thereby increasing possibilities in reducing security and privacy issues

II. SYSTEM ANALYSIS

2.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

Existing system fails to provide good security for shared data in cloud servers, especially in cross-cloud and big data environment. Also, no any existing system provides user defined authorization period and fine grained access during that period. There is no self-destruction of data in present cloud services

DISADVANTAGES

- No privacy ,no good security
- Misuse of sensitive data
- No user defined authorization period.
- No self-destruction of data.

- Loss of Control , Trust Chain in Clouds , Multi-tenancy

2.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system is an iOS application in which registered users can exchange data securely by uploading and downloading files through cloud network. The security is implemented by providing a time frame and a data self destruction mechanism. A time frame is nothing but the expiration time of data in the cloud which is set by the sender while uploading the file. And after the reception of file at the receiver end the self destruction mechanism destroys the file automatically from the cloud server on the expiration of the time frame. All aspects of the network security are treated well by the proposed system.

The user must be authorized to get into the system. For that, If the user is already registered then directly login else register with appropriate details. The user sends message to an existing or new contact along with an expiration time. The sent message will be securely destructed automatically on the expiration of this specified time interval after the receiver has seen the message. The user is provided with an option to save the file into iCloud if the sender has given the permission. AES algorithm is used for encryption and decryption.

ADVANTAGES

The proposed system SECU-ME achieves excellent performance in different prospects.

- Authentication and authorization
- Maximum Privacy
- Confidentiality, integrity, availability
- User defined data expiration time.
- Time based self destruction of data
- Multi tenancy, loss of control is limited.
- User friendly

III. SYSTEM DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION MODELS

3.1 IMPLEMENTATION MODULES

Time based self destruction of data in cloud system consists of the following modules to satisfy specific requirements.

- Registration
- Login
- Send message
- Encryption / Decryption AES
- Cloud Server
- Receive Message
- Save to iCloud

3.1.1. REGISTRATION MODULE

This module displays a quick signup form and allows the users to insert mandatory registration requirement details within the module. This module is often used to increase signups of users. User registers with the system by providing the necessary details like First name, Last name, Email ID, Login id and Password. After successful registration user can login to the system by providing user name and password. Then the user becomes the authorized user for accessing the application.

3.1.2. LOGIN MODULE

A Login is the act, made by a User, of connecting to a system or network service. Usually, a user must enter some credentials, such as his User ID and Password, in order to successfully Login This module checks the authenticity of the user. If the user is already registered then they need to validate themselves by filling login details by their credentials. If the entries filled by user are incorrect then error message is shown. If the entered details are correct then user will be able to login

3.1.3. SEND MESSAGE

This module describes how to use the User Messaging Services. It facilitates the sending of message type's audio, video and text messages. User has to browse and select the location of the file which is to be sent. User has to first encrypt the file. For providing security there is an option for setting time slot for each message sending by the user. By setting such a timeslot, sender is fixing the time, how long the message can be used by the receiver. Either the sender has to specify a time limit up to which the files are available for sharing in the cloud while uploading the files to the cloud. And also the sender can decide whether the receiver can save or download received message to their storage space. If the sender specifies that the particular sending message can be saved by other user, the receiver can save or download it otherwise the receiver can't save only the permission to see or read the message is possible.

3.1.4. ENCRYPTION AND DECRYPTION (AES ALGORITHM)

Encryption is the process of translating plain text data (plain text) into something that appears to be random and meaningless (cipher text). Decryption is the process of converting cipher text back to plain text. To encrypt more than a small amount of data, symmetric key is used. A symmetric key is used during both the encryption and decryption processes. To decrypt a particular piece of cipher text, the key that was used to encrypt the data must be used.

The goal of every encryption algorithm is to make it as difficult as possible to decrypt the generated cipher text without using the key. If a really good encryption algorithm is used, there is no technique significantly better than methodically trying every possible key. For such an algorithm, the longer the key, the more difficult it is to decrypt a piece of cipher text without possessing the key. It is difficult to determine the quality of an encryption algorithm. Algorithms that look promising sometimes turn out to be very easy to break, given the proper attack. When selecting an encryption algorithm, it is a good idea to choose one that has been in use for several years and has successfully resisted all attacks.

The features of AES are as follows –

- Symmetric key symmetric block cipher
- 128-bit data, 128/192/256-bit keys

- Provide full specification and design details
- Software implementable in C and Java

3.1.5. CLOUD SERVER

A cloud server is primarily an Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) based cloud service model. There are two types of cloud server: logical and physical. A cloud server is considered to be logical when it is delivered through server virtualization. In this delivery model, the physical server is logically distributed into two or more logical servers, each of which has a separate OS, user interface and apps, although they share physical components from the underlying physical server. Whereas the physical cloud server is also accessed through the Internet remotely, it isn't shared or distributed. This is commonly known as a dedicated cloud server.

A cloud server is a logical server that is built, hosted and delivered through a cloud computing platform over the Internet. Cloud servers possess and exhibit similar capabilities and functionality to a typical server but are accessed remotely from a cloud service provider.

Cloud server is the database of our system. The messages from the sender are actually uploading to this cloud server and from the cloud server only the receiver receiving the message. In cloud server along with the message the source and destination addresses are storing, i.e. the senders and receivers addresses. It is considered as the database of the system.

3.1.6. RECEIVE MESSAGE

After the process of decryption the receiver receives the messages send by the sender. Data must be decrypted before using. Every messages received should have a time slot assigned by the sender in which if the time to live field is not expired then user can receive the data. User won't be able to access the data after the time to live value expires. After the time out if user is trying to access the data then it gives message-“sorry you cannot access the data”.

If the receiver wants to save or download the received message contents, it is only possible when the sender is granted with permission for that. If the sender allows the permission to save

the message to receiver, can save it to the storage cloud/iCloud otherwise can't save only can see or read the message.

3.1.7. SAVE TO ICLOUD

iCloud is simply a service that keeps all Apple devices in sync. In other words, it can share information between an iPhone, iPad, iPod touch, and a computer. The information on each device is automatically updated to make sure the most current information is available on all devices.. Once the receiver receives the message he can save the message to the iCloud if the sender has turned on the option to save at the time of sending the message. iCloud is apple's cloud storage like an external hard disk in sky, where the data can be stored and received according to needs.

3.2. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig: Architecture diagram

IV.CONCLUSION

We have proposed an excellent idea to secure sensitive and confidential data's that are stored in the cloud server by a self destruction scheme based on time. There are two cases here for providing security; one is setting a time slot for each sending messages which specifies, how long the message can be used by the receiver and the other is sender can decide whether the receiver can save or download received message to their storage space. If the sender specifies that the particular sending message can be saved by other user, the receiver can save or download it otherwise the receiver can't save only the permission to see or read the message is possible. The proposed system is actually an add on to the existing algorithm and these two cases are introduced into the algorithm efficiently. This attempt will reduce the intruders attack on data's and ensuring more security and also it overcomes the problem of delete action by third party, thereby improving the efficiency of system

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